

Macrinus: Nicopolis citygate: AD217-8

Diocletian: AD? (RIC VI.25a)

Diocletian: AD294 (RIC VI.32a)

Diocletian AD298 (RIC VI.42a)

Galerius: AD305-11, camp sacrifice

Licinius I: AD316-7 (RIC VII.15)

Licinius II: AD317 (RIC VII.19)

Licinius II: AD 317 Campgate (Guy Braun)

Constantine I: AD326-7 (RICVII.7)

Constantine I: AD328 (RIC VII.321)

Crispus AD325-6 (RIC VII.64)

Constantius II: AD326-7 (RIC VII.10)

Magnus Maximus: AD 383-8 (RIC IX.36v)

Theodosius I: AD383-8 (RIC.62b)

Acknowledgement:

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